

HOW CAN VARICOSE BE HARMFUL TO YOUR HEALTH?

The varicose veins are harmful to your health as they are unsightly twisted and bulges. Their presence can be noticed by everyone because they are enlarged, bulged veins can cause physical symptoms, including pain and achiness. If you don't treat them on time they will get severe and cause you more problems.

[varicose vein treatment near me clifton](#) has a specialist and experienced team of veins surgeons the mission they have is to eliminate problem veins. Make an appointment with a **vein doctor**, if your varicose veins hurt. To determine the best treatment to eliminate those uncomfortable veins you need to seek a **vein doctor near me**.

Before you go for the treatment of varicose veins or why veins are harmful and cause leg pain. It's needed to know first what exactly varicose veins are. Varicose vein develops when the valve in your vein doesn't work correctly means the blood is not flowing from the veins to the heart and blood clot builds in the veins. It is required for you to take **varicose vein treatment**. In a healthy varicose vein, the valves operate in one direction, carrying blood flow toward the heart while preventing blood from flowing backward. If this process doesn't work properly the veins may hurt you.

What happens to you when varicose veins hurt?

When veins are not working properly they not just provide ache or pain but can also cause:

- Burning or throbbing sensations
- Swelling
- Muscle Cramps
- Pain that occurs when sitting or standing for long periods

- Itching is also another problem that varicose veins give. Itchiness can be irritated.

Varicose veins not only provide these symptoms, but the complications of untreated varicose veins can also be uncomfortable. **Varicose vein treatment clifton** is the place where you can get the best treatment.

If varicose veins left untreated it may lead to ulcers on your legs. A venous ulcer is a slow-healing leg injury. In addition to leg pain, other symptoms you may have are swelling, redness, and drainage. Leg ulcers require proper injury care like debridement, bandaging, and medication. If your varicose veins become a serious problem then it increases the chances of having deep vein thrombosis (DVT), you might experience pain, cramping, swelling, and redness. Not everyone who has varicose veins develops DVT, but research shows that varicose veins increase the risk of DVT.

How can you get rid of varicose veins?

Lifestyle changes, Exercising, avoiding prolonged sitting or standing, and wearing compression stockings can help halt the progression of varicose veins, but what if you need more than conservative options?

At **varicose vein treatment near me**, you may get several different medical interventions for varicose veins which include endovenous ablation and sclerotherapy. [Vein specialist clifton](#) is an expert when it comes to matching the correct treatment to help you reach your aesthetic and health goals.

If your legs hurt due to varicose veins, immediately look for a **vein specialist**. To explore your options, request an appointment online for **vein treatment clifton**.